

Legal Politics of Corruption Criminal Enforcement in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Corruption is the main problem of the deterioration in Indonesia that corruption acts committed by a few of people resulted in the entire nation must bear the consequences. Corruptive behavior has been a culture since ancient times, before and after independence, in the era of the Old Order, New Order, and continuing to the Reformation era, so that special strategies are needed in its eradication. This research is a normative legal research using the statute and historical approach. Legal politics in the enforcement of corruption in Indonesia by forming several laws and regulations and the movement to eradicate corruption. The improvement is good in the substance of its rules, the eradication movement which is part of the nation's culture, and improvement in its institutional aspects, so that it is expected to be able to eradicate corruption with efficient and effectiveness.

KEYWORD: Legal politics, Corruption, Criminal Enforcement

INTRODUCTION

Corruption is the main problem of the deterioration of the nation, corrupt acts committed by a handful of people resulted in the entire nation must bear the consequences. Corruptive behavior in Indonesia originally started by central-level officials, but now almost in every level, both central and regional officials, bureaucrats, and entrepreneurs commit corruption. In general, the more apprehensive corrupt behavior act not only by individuals but also carried out by groups (in congregation) and systemic.¹

Corruptive behavior had become a culture since ancient times, before and after independence, in the era of the Old Order, New Order, and the Reformation era. Various attempts had been made to eradicate corruption, but the results are still not satisfactory. Historical researchers in Indonesia are less interested in focusing their studies on the problem of corruption related to power carried out by royal nobles, sultanates, officials and the Dutch government itself. Researchers are more interested in the study of political and socio-cultural historical issues rather than the problem of corrupt behavior, even though the impact of this culture of corruption is able to influence and even change the political map, both on a local and national scale. These corrupt systems and patterns teach fraudulent, obscene, immoral, opportunistic and other behaviors, which in turn result in poverty and social inequality in society.

The commitment to eradicate corruption is an important milestone in the governance of a civilized country. With this statement there should be no doubt in the Corruption Eradication because the president himself will lead it, but the reality is not as easy as the Corruption Eradication said, the commitment to eradicate Corruption is very difficult to do. For this reason, the author takes the title Legal political Enforcement of Corruption in Indonesia. This title is taken with the consideration that the corrupt behavior of Indonesian bureaucrats can disrupt the national economy and ultimately lead to social inequality and poverty in Indonesian society.

METHODS

This research is a normative juridical research, using a historical approach and a statutory approach.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Understanding Legal political.

Legal political is the policy of state administrators about what is used as a criterion to punish something, in this case the policy can be related to the formation of law, the application of law and enforcement itself. Padmo Wahjono defines legal politics as the basic policy that determines the direction, form and content of the law to be formed.² In line with what was explained by Padmo Wahjono, another legal expert Soedarto explained the notion of political politics is as follows.

Legal political is the policy of the state through the state agencies that are authorized to eradicate the Corruption of the desired regulations, which are expected to be used to express what is contained in society and to achieve what is aspired.²

The legal politics of one country is different from other countries, this difference is due to differences in historical backgrounds, world-views, sociocultural, and political will of each government. Legal politics are local and particular, that is, it only applies from and for certain countries and are not universal, but those do not mean that the legal politics of a country ignores the politics of

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international law. Understanding the politics of law includes the process of making and implementing laws that can indicate the nature and direction in which the law will be built. Legal politics provide the basis for the process of legal formation that is more appropriate to the situation and conditions, culture and values that develop in society by taking into account the needs of the community for the law itself.³ Legal politics can be divided into two dimensions, namely legal politics which is the basic reason for the holding of a statutory regulation, and the purpose or reason that appears behind the enactment of a statutory regulation. Legal politics have a very important role in making laws and regulations, that is as a reason why it is necessary to form a statutory regulation, and to determine what is intended to be translated into legal sentences and to formulate articles.

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Culture of corruption has ingrained throughout the history of the Indonesian nation as has been described, apparently relapsing again in the Post-Independence Era, both in the Old Order Era, the New Order and Reformation. The pressure point for the problem of corruption actually lies in the government's seriousness in the effort to eradicate corruption. This paper will discuss briefly the Eradication of Corruption in the era before the occupation (the kingdom of the archipelago), the colonial period, the old order, the new order and reformation. Each of the following will be explained one by one, as follows.

1. Pre-colonial Period

The history of the Indonesian people shows that in the period before Indonesian independence, it was colored by various cultures or corrupt traditions / behaviors. This behavior can occur because of the motives of power, greed, wealth and women. In searching history, it is seen that the tradition of corruption with the struggle for power is very prominent, for example in the Kingdom of Singosari until seven descendants take revenge against each other in fighting over power: Anusapati, Tohjoyo, Ranggawuni, Mahesa Wongateleng and so on. During the Majapahit kingdom there was also a rebellion or power struggle including the revolt of Kuti, Nambi, Suro and others, whereas during the Demak kingdom there was a feud between Joko Tingkir and Hariyo Penangsang, the Kingdom of Banten with the Sultan Haji case seizing the throne from his father Sultan Ageng Tirtoyoso. Several times the transfer of power in the archipelago has colored the history of corruption in Indonesia.

2. The Dutch Colonial Period

The habit of taking tribute from the small people carried out by the King of Java was imitated by the Dutch when they controlled the archipelago (1800-1942) minus the British Age (1811-1816). As a result of this policy many people's resistance against the Dutch occurred. For example, the Diponegoro resistance (1825-1830), Imam Bonjol (1821-1837), Aceh (1873-1904) and others. But even sadder is the oppression of the indigenous population by the Indonesian people themselves. For example, the case of fraud in the implementation of the Stelsel Cultuur System which literally means the culture system, although the main purpose of the system is to cultivate productive plants in the community so that the results are able to improve people's welfare and contribute to the Dutch treasury, but in reality it is very alarming.

3. Old Order Period

History of Corruption Eradication has been carried out since the Old Order government, when efforts to fill independence showed symptoms of abuse. Symptoms like this were first evident during the period of physical struggle to defend the newly proclaimed republic. At that time the term corruption became very popular in society, and was very worrying. The legal provisions contained in the Criminal Code were found to be ineffective in eradicating corruption, as a result many corruptors could not be brought to court because their actions did not meet the formula contained in the Criminal Code.

Departing from this fact, on April 9, 1957, the Army Chief of Staff as the military ruler at that time issued Regulation No. Prt / PM-06/1957. After being enacted for a while in its development it turned out that this military ruler regulation was felt to be ineffective enough, so it needed to be supplemented with regulations regarding ownership of property which was then regulated in Military Rule Regulation No. Prt / PM-08/1957 dated May 22, 1957. This regulation is intended to obtain maximum results for the interests of the state in its efforts to eradicate corruption. With this regulation the military authorities have the authority to inspect the assets of every person or entity in their area, whose wealth is obtained suddenly and is very suspicious.

The enactment of Law No. 74 of 1957 concerning Dangerous Conditions on April 17, 1958, became the basis for the Juanda Cabinet to form a Corruption Eradication Agency called the State Apparatus Retooling Committee (PARAN). This body is led by A.H. Nasution and assisted by two members namely Professor M. Yamin and Roeslan Abdulgani.⁴ Based on Law No. 74 of 1957, the military authorities replaced the existing regulations which were replaced by the Army War Ruling Regulation No. Prt./Peperpu/013/1958 concerning Investigation, Prosecution and Investigation of Criminal Corruption and Property Ownership for areas controlled by the Army, and for areas within the territory of the Navy the Military Regulatory Regulations are also established. Navy No. Prt / zl / 17 April 17, 1958 (announced in BN Number 42/58).⁵

Although the two regulations of the military authorities were made so that in a short period of time they could expose rampant corruption, but in the practical level the State Apparatus Retooling Committee received a lot of resistance, so that was unable to do much and was handed back to the Djuanda Cabinet. Within two years after the enactment of the Central War Authority, then on June 9, 1960 the government issued Government Regulation in Lieu of Law Number 24 of 1960 Concerning Investigation,

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Prosecution and Examination of Criminal Acts of Corruption, State Gazette No. 72 of 1960⁶ and in 1961 with Law No. 1 of 1961, Government regulations in lieu of Law No. 24 Prp of 1960 the legal status was confirmed as Law No. 24 Prp. 1960 concerning the Investigation, Prosecution and Examination of Corruption, State Agency No. 72 of 1960.⁷ Bambang Poernomo in that connection said that the renewal that was held in the substance of Law No. 24 Prp of 1960 has given a clue about how complex the eradication of corruption crime that has a veiled pattern of behavior and has a target in the political, economic, financial and socio-cultural fields.⁸

Then in 1963 through Presidential Decree Number 275 of 1963 the Operation Budhi was launched, in this operation the government again appointed A.H. Nasution, who was then serving as Coordinating Minister for Defense and Security and assisted by Wiryo Prodjodikoro as the controller of the operation. Through Operation Budhi, the government hopes that the perpetrators of corruption can be dragged by the judiciary, especially the perpetrators of corruption within the bodies of companies and other state institutions deemed prone to corrupt practices and collusion.⁴ Political reasons caused stagnation and effectiveness in the implementation of Operation Budhi, as in the investigation of the case of Pertamina's Managing Director who had fled abroad and other Pertamina Directors refused to be examined on the grounds that there was no letter of assignment from superiors. Although managed to save state finances reached more or less Rp. 11 Billion, Operation Budhi was later disbanded through an announcement read by Subandrio and replaced by the Supreme Command of Retooling Revolutionary Apparatus with president Soekarno as chairman and assisted by Soebandrio and Lieutenant General Ahmad Yani.⁴ Although there have been several changes in laws and regulations and several times established the Corruption Eradication Institute, but during the period between 1960-1970 the development and increase in the potential for criminal acts of corruption was felt to continue with great progress.⁹

4. The New Order Period

During the New Order government issued the most regulations to eradicate corruption, but unfortunately it did not apply effectively. In a state address in front of DPR/MPR members on August 16, 1967, President Soeharto blamed the Old Order regime for being unable to eradicate corruption because all economic and political policies were centered in the palace. The speech signaled that Suharto was determined to root out corruption at its roots. As a form of this determination, the Corruption Eradication Team (TPK) was formed, chaired by the Attorney General by issuing Presidential Decree Number 28 of 1967 concerning the Formation of the Corruption Eradication Team.

In implementation, the team was not able to carry out the Corruption Eradication totally, it could even be said to be almost not functioning. This regulation even triggered various forms of protests and demonstrations starting in 1969 and culminating in 1970 which was then marked by the formation of Commission IV whose task was to analyze problems in the bureaucracy and issue recommendations to overcome them. Still in the same year, Indonesia's former first vice president Bung Hatta gave rise to the discourse that corruption had been entrenched in Indonesia. Corruption has become the behavior of a new regime led by Suharto, even though the age of this regime is still so young. Hatta felt the ideals of the founders of the Republic had been betrayed. Corruption is very detrimental to the country's finances and economy and impedes national development, and Law No. 24 Prp. in 1960 concerning the Investigation, Prosecution and Examination of Corruption Crimes did not run effectively so it needed to be replaced. During the Indonesian Independence Day speech on August 17, 1970, the Soeharto government issued Law Number 3 of 1971 concerning the Eradication of Corruption, promulgated in Jakarta on March 29, 1971. This Act addresses the Corruption Eradication of maximum life imprisonment and a maximum fine of IDR 30 million for all offenses categorized as corruption. Complementing this law, one of the Indonesian Broad Guidelines of State Policy's contains the people's willingness to eradicate corruption. The implementation of the Indonesian Broad Guidelines of State Policy was leaked because the management of the country was marked by a lot of fraud and leakage of the state budget in all sectors. State organs such as parliament which have oversight functions are made weak, the House of Representative's budget is determined by the government so that the oversight function is no longer available. The judiciary was created similarly by the New Order regime, so that there was no power left to be able to try corruption cases independently. The power of civil society was spayed, the New Order authorities slowly limited the space for the people and intervened to maintain their power.

In 1970, driven by the seriousness of the corruption eradication team in eradicating corruption such as Suharto's commitment, students and students staged a protest to protest the existence of the corruption eradication team. State companies such as Bulog, Pertamina, the Ministry of Forestry have been highlighted by the public because they are considered to be a hotbed of corruption. The rise of the wave of protests and demonstrations conducted by students, finally responded to Suharto by forming a Four Committee consisting of old figures who were considered clean and authoritative such as Prof. Johannes, IJ Kasimo, Mr. Wilopo and A Tjokroaminoto. Their main task is to clean up, among others, the Department of Religion, Bulog, Commanditaire Vennootschap (CV) Waringin, Mantrust Ltd., Telkom, and Pertamina, but this committee is only a toothless tiger because its findings about allegations of corruption in Pertamina have not been responded to by the government.

Regulations continue to be tightened with Presidential Decree Number 52 of 1971 concerning Tax Reporting of Officials and Civil Servants, then Presidential Instruction Number 9 of 1977 concerning Order Control and Law Number 11 of 1980 concerning Criminal Acts of Bribery. However, in its implementation it cannot perform Corruption Eradication optimally, it can even be said

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to be almost non-functional. In an effort to eliminate corrupt practices carried out by persons in the Government apparatus that are not based on regulations such as illegal levies in various forms and to improve and enhance the usefulness and results of the Government apparatus, it is necessary to have comprehensive and continuing control measures. continuously in the body of the Government apparatus. In order for the enforcement of these measures to achieve maximum results, it is deemed necessary to provide guidance as a guideline for their implementation. At the time of President Soeharto's administration, the Instruction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia Number 9 of 1977 concerning Orderly Operations was issued.

Admiral Sudomo was appointed as the Corruption Eradication Stamps, the Operation of Order was formed with the task of combating corruption. This policy only gave birth to cynicism in society, not long after the Operation of Order was formed there arose a quite sharp difference of opinion between Sudomo and Nasution regarding the choice of methods or methods of Eradicating Corruption. Nasution is of the opinion that if he wants to succeed in eradicating corruption it must start from the top, Nasution advised Admiral Sudomo to start from himself. Over time, Operation of Order also disappeared without a trace.

5. Reformation Period

In 1998 appeared People's Consultative Assembly Decree Number XI/MPR/1998 concerning Clean and Collusion of Corruption and Nepotism Free State Management. In the context of eradicating corruption and implementing People's Consultative Assembly Decree Number XI/MPR/1998, President BJ Habibie issued Law Number 28 of 1999 concerning State Administration that is Clean and Free of Collusion of Corruption and Nepotism. In addition, Law Number 3 of 1971 concerning Eradication of Corruption Crimes is no longer in accordance with the development of legal needs in the community, because it needs to be replaced in a way that Corruption Eradication is more effective, President BJ Habibie issued Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning Eradication of Corruption. ratified on August 16, 1999. This Law Number 31 of 1999 came up with the consideration that acts of corruption were very detrimental to the country's finances or the country's economy and hampered national development, so they must be eradicated in order to create a just and prosperous society based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. As a result of criminal acts of corruption that have occurred so far also hampered the growth and continuity of national development that demanded high efficiency.

The next president, Abdurrahman Wahid, in the context of implementing People's Consultative Assembly Decree Number XI/MPR/1998, formed a Joint Team for Corruption Crime Prevention, with Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2000 concerning the Combined Team for Eradicating Corruption. This Corruption Eradication Joint Team in accordance with article 11 PP No. 19 of 2000 has the duty and authority to coordinate investigations and prosecutions of anyone suspected of committing corrupt acts that is difficult to prove. In addition to the above authority, the Corruption Eradication Joint Team also has the authority to request information from banks regarding the suspect's finances in accordance with applicable laws and regulations, asking banks to block the suspect's savings account; open, inspect, confiscate letters and mails by post, telecommunications, or other devices suspected of having links with corruption under investigation, conduct wiretapping, propose bans and submit recommendations to the suspect's leaders / superiors with sufficient evidence to suspend suspects from his position. Besides that, Abdurrahman also appointed Baharudin Lopa as Minister of Justice, who later became the Attorney General. The Attorney General's Office had taken concrete steps to uphold corruption law, many high-ranking corruptors were examined and made suspects at the time.

In the midst of eradicating the corruption of team members, the perpetrators of corruption conducted a judicial review attempt to the Supreme Court and were approved, so Corruption Eradication Joint Team was finally dissolved. At that moment, Indonesia experienced a setback in its efforts. Corruption Eradication (KPK). In the development of his leadership in addition to disbanding Corruption Eradication Joint Team, Abdurrahman was also considered to be part of the community who could not demonstrate leadership that could support the Corruption Eradication effort. The penchant for holding meetings outside the presidential agenda even in inappropriate places in his capacity as president, gave rise to public suspicion that Abdurrahman was conducting a high-level bargaining process. The process of examining cases of alleged corruption involving tycoon Sofyan Wanandi was terminated with a Warrant for Investigation from Attorney General Marzuki Darusman. In the end Gus Dur was plagued by the Buloggate case, so Abdurrahman was ousted from the presidency not through a constitutional mechanism, Megawati replaced him through what was called a political compromise. Laksamana Sukardi as the State Minister for State-Owned Corporation did not escape talks in the community because of his policy of selling state assets.

In the context of realizing a just, prosperous and prosperous society, the eradication of corruption that has occurred up to now cannot be carried out optimally, so it needs to be improved professionally, intensively, and continuously. Government institutions that handle cases of corruption have not functioned effectively and efficiently in eradicating criminal acts of corruption, and in accordance with the provisions of Article 43 of Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning Eradication of Corruption Crimes as amended by Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning Amendment to Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning Eradication of Corruption, an independent Corruption Eradication Commission must be formed with the task and authority to eradicate corruption, the issuance of Law Number 30 of 2002 concerning Corruption Eradication Commission, which was ratified on December 27, 2002 by Megawati Sukarnoputri.

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Megawati's reign was seen with visible decreasing authority of the law, in which what stood out was the authority of power. Just look at how easily a problematic conglomerate can deceive the law enforcement authorities by reason of seeking treatment abroad. The granting of Warrant for Investigation to Prajogo Pangestu, Marimutu Sinivasan, Sjamsul Nursalim, The Nien King, Samadikun Hartono's escape from the snare of executing the Supreme Court's decision, the granting of Master Settlement and Acquisition Agreement (MSAA) facilities to conglomerates whose debts were stalled, became strong evidence that the government elite was not serious in efforts to eradicate corruption. The community considers that the government still provides protection to big businessmen who contribute to the bankruptcy of the national economy. The government has increasingly lost its authority, and recently corruption cases have also spread in a number of Reform-era Regional House of Representatives.

During Megawati Soekarno Putri's leadership, various corruption cases evaporated and ended with stories that did not satisfy the community. The community began to doubt the government's commitment to eradicate corruption at that time because many Special operation, Bulog, for example, were suspected of corruption but could not be completed. In the midst of the very low public trust in the state institutions that are supposed to deal with corruption, the Megawati government later formed the Corruption Eradication Commission. The establishment of this institution was a legal breakthrough on the impasse of Corruption Eradication efforts in this country, and which later became the forerunner to the Corruption Eradication Commission.

The long journey to eradicate corruption is like getting a breath of fresh air when a state institution emerges with clear duties and authorities to eradicate corruption. Although previously, this was arguably late from the agenda mandated by the provisions of Article 43 of Law Number 31 of 1999 as amended by Law Number 20 of 2001. Discussion of the KPK Bill could be said to be a form of the seriousness of the Megawati Sukarnoputri government in Combating Corruption. The delay in the discussion of the bill was motivated by many reasons. Namely a change in the constitution which implies a change in the constitutional map, and the tendency of the legislative heavy on the House of Representatives, as well as the tyranny of the House of Representatives. One of the delays in the discussion of the KPK Bill is that it is also caused by internal problems which plagued the political system in Indonesia in the reform era.

In the era of President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono, the vision of Corruption Eradication was reflected in the initial steps taken by issuing Presidential Instruction No. 5 of 2004 and then continued with the preparation of the National Action Plan for Corruption Eradication prepared by Bappenas. The NAP Eradication Corruption took effect in 2004-2009. By using the paradigm of the legal system, the Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono government benefited from an established legal system and the existence of eradicating corruption through Law Number 30 of 2002, Corruption Court which is separate from general courts, international support, and legal instruments that support each other national law and international law.

In order to create a just and prosperous society based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, the government together with the community take steps to prevent and eradicate corruption in a systematic and sustainable manner. Corruption is no longer a local problem, but it is a transnational phenomenon that affects the whole community and the economy so that it is important that international cooperation exists to prevent and eradicate it, including the recovery or return of assets resulting from corruption. International cooperation needs to be supported by integrity, accountability and good government management. The Indonesian people have been actively involved in the efforts of the international community to prevent and eradicate corruption by signing the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, 2003 (United Nations Anti-Corruption Convention, 2003), the ratification of Law Number 7 of 2006 concerning Ratification of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, 2003 (2003 United Nations Anti-Corruption Convention). ratified on April 18, 2006 by Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono.

In an effort to strengthen the evidence in eradicating criminal acts of corruption in court, Law Number 13 of 2006 concerning the Protection of Witnesses and Victims, dated 11 August 2006, State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Year 2006 Number 64. Witnesses are one of the legal evidences in the judicial process criminal. Information from Witnesses and / or Victims who have heard, seen, or experienced the occurrence of a criminal act in an effort to find and find clarity about the criminal act carried out by the perpetrators of criminal acts needs to be protected. Law enforcers in seeking and finding clarity about criminal acts committed by criminal offenders often experience difficulties because they cannot present Witnesses and/or Victims due to threats, both physical and psychological from certain parties, so that protection for Witnesses and / or Victims is required, very important presence in the criminal justice process.

Services to the public and law enforcement carried out in the context of administering the state and government are an inseparable part of efforts to create good, clean and efficient governance to improve welfare and create justice and legal certainty for all citizens as referred to in the Act Basis of the Republic of Indonesia in 1945. Supervision of services carried out by state and government administrators is an important element in the effort to create good, clean, and efficient government and at the same time is an implementation of democratic principles that need to be developed and applied in order to prevent and eliminate abuse of authority by government officials country and government. By paying attention to the aspirations that develop in the community in order to realize the apparatus of state and government officials that are effective and efficient, honest, clean, open and free from corruption, collusion and nepotism, it is necessary to establish an Ombudsman institution of the Republic of Indonesia; then President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono signed Law Number 37 of 2008 concerning the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia, ratified on October 7, 2008.

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Even though witness and victim protection has been postponed, the guarantee of protection for witnesses and victims has not yet proceeded in accordance with the Corruption Eradication. Guaranteed protection for witnesses and victims has an important role in the criminal justice process so that witness and victim testimonies are given free from fear and threats to reveal a criminal act. To increase the overall effort to disclose a crime, especially transnational organized crime, it is also necessary to provide protection for witnesses, perpetrators, reporters, and experts. Several provisions in Law Number 13 of 2006 concerning Witness and Victim Protection need to be adjusted to the development of the community's legal needs, so it is necessary to establish a Law on Amendment to Law Number 13 of 2006 concerning Protection of Witnesses and Victims with Law Number 31 2014 concerning Amendment to Law Number 13 of 2006 concerning Protection of Witnesses and Victims.

In the effort to implement the prevention and eradication of corruption as mandated in Presidential Regulation Number 55 Year 2012 concerning the National Strategy for Long-Term Corruption Prevention and Eradication in 2012-2025 and Medium-Term Year 2012-2014 and as an implementation the preparation of Prevention actions is issued. President of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2 of 2014 concerning the Prevention and Eradication of Corruption Act of 2014, March 21, 2014. In the era of Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono, commitment and efforts in preventing and eradicating corruption have always been the government's priority. Various efforts have been made by the Government such as structuring policies and regulations, both in the form of instructions / directives and legislation, improving governance, improving the process of public services, transparency and accountability in the management of state finances, including saving state finances / assets.

At the international level, the Government is also actively involved in various global initiatives to fight corruption. One of them is through the ratification of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption through Law Number 7 of 2006 concerning Ratification of the 2003 United Nations Convention Against Corruption (Convention of the United Nations Anti-Corruption, 2003). As a consequence of the ratification, the Government of Indonesia has stipulated Presidential Regulation Number 55 Year 2012 concerning the National Strategy for Corruption Prevention and Long-Term Corruption Eradication in 2012-2025 and Medium-Term Year 2012-2014. The strategies contained in the Corruption Prevention and Eradication include prevention strategies, law enforcement strategies, harmonization strategies for laws and regulations, international cooperation strategies and saving assets, educational strategies and anti-corruption culture, and reporting mechanism strategies, which in practice only focus on preventing corruption.

In the era of his administration, President Joko Widodo has signed Presidential Instruction Number 10 of 2016 and Presidential Regulation Number 54 of 2018. Presidential Instruction Number 10 of 2016 concerning Actions to Prevent and Eradicate Corruption in 2016 and 2017. This Presidential Instruction focuses on the matter of preventing criminal acts of corruption and law enforcement in the field of Corruption Eradication (KPK), so that the Head of Indonesian Ministry of National Development Planning at that time stressed that ministries, institutions, and regional governments must implement the Presidential Instruction. In order to carry out Presidential Instruction Number 10 of 2016 the implementation strategy is needed. Taking into account the framework of prevention efforts that are more focused, measurable, and results-oriented and impacted, the government views that Presidential Regulation Number 55 of 2012 concerning the National Strategy for the Prevention and Eradication of Long-Term Corruption 2012-2025 and Medium-Term Year 2012-2014 is no longer in accordance with developments. Based on these considerations, on July 20, 2018, President Joko Widodo signed the Presidential Regulation Number 54 Year 2018 concerning the National Strategy for Corruption Prevention (link: Presidential Regulation Number 54 Year 2018). According to this Perpres, the focus of the National Strategy on Corruption Prevention includes: a. licensing and trade system; b. finance; and c. law enforcement and bureaucratic reform, which are elaborated through the Corruption Eradication Action.

In the framework of organizing the Corruption Eradication Strategy, a National Team for the Prevention of Corruption, hereinafter referred to as the National Team for Corruption Eradication, is in accordance with Article 4 paragraph (1) of this Regulation. The Corruption Eradication National Team, according to this Perpres, consists of ministers who carry out government affairs in the field of national development planning, ministers who hold government affairs in the country, ministers who carry out government affairs in the field of the state apparatus, heads of non-structural institutions that hold support to the President and Vice The President in implementing the controlling of national priority programs and managing strategic issues, as well as the leadership elements of the Corruption Eradication Commission.

Even though the Presidential Instruction and Presidential Decree were issued, in the era of JokoWidodo's government, corruption was rampant, as evidenced by the many aides of the President (Ministers, Governors, Regents, and others) and Legislative members (including political party leaders) who were arrested and processed in court. with a Catch-Hand Operation conducted by the National Team for Corruption Eradication. The role of the National Team for Corruption Eradication in eradicating corruption is very prominent, even the president feels overwhelmed to control the National Team for Corruption Eradication. In order to stem the very prominent role of the National Team for Corruption Eradication in law enforcement, the government together with the House of Representatives then discussed the revision of the National Team for Corruption Eradication Law at the initiative of the House of Representatives. It was not until one month that the law was passed by the Parliament on 17 September 2019.

With the ratification of the revision of the National Team for Corruption Eradicationlaw, a massive wave of demonstrations by students and all Indonesian people rejected the ratification of the law, and asked the president to issue a Perpu on the cancellation

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of the ratification of the law. Until the 1 month deadline since the president was not named, the law was promulgated, thus enacting the president's signature with Law Number 19 Year 2019 concerning Second Amendment to Law Number 30 Year 2002 Concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission, October 17 2019, LNRI 2019 Number 197. With this law the authority of the National Team for Corruption Eradication was reduced, the authority of the National Team for Corruption Eradication to conduct wiretapping which was the National Team for Corruption Eradication's mainstay in eradicating corruption was reduced. In conducting wiretapping, the National Team for Corruption Eradication must obtain the approval of the supervisory board, and the supervisory board can approve the wiretapping request, a case title must be carried out, even though all years in the Criminal Procedure Code that the case title can be carried out if there is already at least 2 pieces of evidence. At this time the eradication of corruption is the lowest point in Indonesia.

CONCLUSION

Corruption is the main cause of the deterioration of the Indonesian nation, corrupt acts committed by a handful of people resulted in the entire nation must bear the consequences. In eradicating, various efforts have been made, starting from the material aspects of the legislation, culture and legal system of the institution that handles it, but until now it has not shown any encouraging symptoms. Not yet found the right formulation to eradicate corruption in Indonesia.

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